

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Alkali****FIRST NAME: Dauda****PROGRAM CODE: MTSD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did not use Zotero to insert some references

The author did use Grammarly Premium

The author used the following software: Word 365

PROFESSIONAL WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

For centuries, language has been an essential part of national culture. To further pass on the cultural heritage, people have tried to teach their tongues to the younger generation with an emphasis on pronunciation, spellings, and so forth. While blending with modernization, they have sought to balance their heritage with imported words and ideas as well as integrating them due to globalization. In recent years, organizations, government, and private alike have seen the need to situate the importance of professional writing as one of the pillars for human capital development. The influence of consistent formats and styles of writing official communication between organizations or countries could be immense as they seek to achieve specific objectives. “An academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence” (EUCLID 2019, 1). As persuasion is one of the objectives of diplomacy, organizations need to employ competent writers. I, therefore, see the various styles of writing, the spelling, and punctuation rules, among others contained in this course material, as an attempt to pass on the knowledge of the English language. The experience of this course will be helpful to us, not only as students but as representatives of various organizations and countries. Just as we ponder over the saying ‘are leaders born or made?’, I wonder if the case is the same for writers.

2) A GOOD ESSAY WRITING

One cannot overemphasize the need to write a good essay as we encounter it one way or the other. Over the past years, I have written several reports, proposals, manuals, Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs), and so forth, but never have I come across the

need to adopt an International style or a standard format. Perhaps this was so because the write-ups were non-academic and usually prepared for the consumption of local staff and not international actors. The content of this coursepack has given me a fresh insight, making me ponder over the blunders I have done in the past.

The basics of essay writing captured my attention as the steps outlined were self-explanatory. Starting the work on time will surely ensure ample time for research, organizing ideas, drafting, and editing, among other things (Ibid.). Usually, the desire to get things done quickly prevents them from being done correctly. As the famous saying goes, "Procrastination is the thief of time." One has to manage his time well to maximize productivity and produce good results.

As technology evolves, information technology tools for guiding writers have come in handy. Having come across several applications in this course, such as Zotero, JSTOR, and even the basic ones like Grammarly, I must acknowledge the fact that, when mastered, one will produce excellent essays. I found the 14-minute Vimeo video on the use of Zotero very helpful, and I have begun practicing its usage. I have downloaded the relevant applications and followed the instructions in the video on managing styles from document preferences and inserting citations, among other things. The introductory video on how to save papers, avoiding common mistakes, and even using some facilities in Microsoft Office Word, such as setting Proofing language, was equally very enlightening.

Just as an expert in any field would detest another person taking credit for their work, plagiarism has been tagged as a serious academic offense as it is not only wrong and unethical but also unfair to the original writer (EUCLID 2019, 5). I have often wondered how one will cope with citing numerous sources as we know some things without even remembering where and how we learned them. I overcame this dilemma when I came across "When NOT to cite" (EUCLID 2019, 9). I learned that information that is common knowledge or that had been repeated in many different sources could be assumed to be common knowledge, as such needs no citation (EUCLID 2019, 10).

3) WRITING STYLES

I found the rules of thumb for writing papers, and literature review to be fascinating as they provided didactic and straightforward guides to effective writing. I can argue that brevity is an art; as such, one must master it to write with clarity, using short sentences and avoiding long paragraphs as well as refraining from using sweeping generalities. Other aspects I found intriguing were the introduction of stylistic variety, taking one's views seriously, reading the paper out loud, among others (EUCLID 2019, 14). The 11 essential reminders mentioned in the literature review have also hit the nail on the head. They have provided useful insights to the proper use of commas, an indication of possession by appropriate placement of an "s," the use of active voice rather than the passive, omitting unnecessary words, among others (EUCLID 2019, 17). The most exciting thing I learned in this chapter is the inclusion of 'comma' before the conjunction. The argument posed by the instructor that the exclusion of the comma can sometimes increase ambiguity in the sentence is entirely plausible.

The Chicago Manual of Style (PMS) provided useful tips on the use of abbreviations when beginning a sentence and when using traditional honorifics and initials as well as when using scholarly abbreviations (EUCLID 2019, 35). I must say that if not for those tips, I would have used abbreviations such as e.g. and etc in this paper. On capitalization, perhaps the only place that was not very clear is why capitalize *Central America* and not central Europe or central Asia? (EUCLID 2019, 45).

4) BRITISH VS AMERICAN ENGLISH

As a citizen of a country that was colonized by the British, I grew up assuming I used more of British English than American. However, having studied this coursepack, I have formed a new opinion as I have been mixing the two all along. While I was very aware of the common differences in spellings like colour and color, centre and center, I mixed up organization and organisation. I was also unaware of some differences in the use of punctuations. Such differences, no doubt, form a challenge that calls for more attention in future writings. On the format for dates, my country never adopted a particular format. Consequently, different people use formats that are convenient for them (EUCLID 2019, 35). Perhaps the careless mix of the two formats is as a result of globalization as well as other factors that are gradually phasing out the British English from its colonies. The higher ratio of native English speakers in the United States (U.S) compared to the United Kingdom played a vital role in the dominance of American English over British English. Other reasons are the magnitude of publishing industries in the U.S, the international political and economic position of the U.S as well as the wealth of the U.S compared to the U.K. Furthermore, the magnitude of higher education in the U.S, the appeal of the American culture on language and habits, and the magnitude of global mass media and media technology influenced this dominance. (EUCLID 2019, 27). In this coursepack, I observed that some of the differences mentioned examples but no mention of the format, such as those mentioned under different spelling with the same pronunciation on page 28.

5) CONCLUSION

I am beginning to understand why the course instructor mentioned in the welcome e-mail he sent to me that enrolling in Euclid University is one of the critical decisions of my life. The course pack and the related videos were beneficial and will guide one in mastering the art of writing. While I found most of the course to be refreshing, engaging, and insightful, only but a few aspects such as the British and American format usage are a bit fuzzy. While I struggle to understand and eventually master the use of Zotero, the styles of writing, and others, I am optimistic that one day, I would beat my chest and say, 'I was trained by the best!'. And with this, I would conveniently say writers, can be made, just like leaders. Giving veracity the adage, "Practice makes perfect," I will conclude by saying what is needed to make a professional writer are the necessary components, dedication, research, and practice.

REFERENCE

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd Ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

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